

DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING IN COMMUNICATION WITH THE HELP OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND METHODS

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Abstract. For the development of communicative communication in English in this article there is talk about the pedagogical technologies used and their effectiveness. Thus one has the series provides a complete overview of pedagogical technology.

Key words: pedagogical technology, foreign language teaching methods, methods and techniques, «Gold fish "exercise," Art Gallery", taxonomy of Bloom.

Technology from the Greek word "techné" derived from "skill", "art" means meaning something of a production methods used in the field (methods) is a complex. Notable pedagogical scholars U.Tolipov, N.Saydahmedov, T.Madumarov, M.Ka pedagogical according to the views of the moldinovs the history of the development of technologies to 4 stages division:

Stage 1. In pedagogy the emergence of the concept of "pedagogical technique" be (30s of the 20th century).

Stage 2. Technical training the emergence and use of tools (40-60 years of the 20th century).

Stage 3. Training technologies creation and pedagogy of the new generation to give rise to the scientific foundations of technology arrival (70-80 years of the XX century).

Stage 4. Pedagogical technologies creation of scientific and theoretical foundations, new the emergence of the research direction and scientific formation of schools (90 years of the XX century Early 21st century).

B.Bloom (training goals taxonomy), B.Skinner (program teaching system), LLarsen(audiovisual education, D.Finn(teaching technology, D.Kratval (educational technologies) and S.Peypert(Programmed education) pedagogical technology are considered the founders of the idea.Especially, the emergence, formation of various scientific ideas in the field of pedagogical technologies and the geography of application to practice 60-70 expanded further in the years.

In European states and special in the developed countries of Asia pedagogical publications,associations, scientific research institutes and centers were established. One From the 80s by Russian scientists from now on, the

scientific basis of pedagogical Technologies began to be widely applied.

As a vivid example of this V.M.Monakhov's "axiomatic approach", V.P.Bespalco's "personality-oriented education", M.A.Choshanov's "Muamolli-modular teaching technology", V.F.Shatalov's". Based on the iconic models of educational material technology to accelerate education " as we can get their works, the reason is that they have the concept of pedagogical technology scientific on pedagogical grounds given.Also in Uzbekistan from the 90s starting from pedagogical technologies early scientific research work created. N. S. Saidahmedov, J. Yoldashev,R.Jo ' ra Yew, U.Nishanaliyev, A.Pardayev, U.Tolipov and scientific analysis by others studied.On the educational system in our country "Modern Education", " Science and technology" magazines and " innovative technologies centers are established.We also have the question arises " What is pedagogical technology himself?".This question is asked differently by the people of science opinions expressed.

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First of all, what pedagogical technology says we need to find a broader answer to the question. This term is different from many scholars annotated. As we noted above, this is for those who do not reject each other complements. In Particular, V. Bespoic said that pedagogy implementation of the educational process of technology the enhancer described as a meaningful technique. U independent of teacher skill the process of forming the personality of the reader it is a project. M.V. Clarín, on the other hand, refers to the term as in achieving pedagogical goals personal facilities, equipment used and to be in practice in methodological tools opinion that denotes the systematic sum and order reported. V.M. Monakhov " Pedagogical technology-by creating the necessary conditions the educational process of the student and teacher design, organization and transfer all-round pedagogical activity on is a thoughtful model, " commented.

It is no secret that the content of education, purpose and his duties expanded as periods passed, and his shapes and methods are also improved is getting. Therefore, the practice of Education pedagogical on the basis of developing needs the concept of technology originated. This the main processing material in technology Mental, spiritual, moral qualities of the educator are known to them by the educator different effects on the way to achieving goals held. The following applies to pedagogical technology let us give short and generalized definitions can: Pedagogical technology is a harmonious person formation activities, forms of Education setting the optimization task, the whole the process of mastering training and knowledge technical resources and interaction of people applying taking into account their relationship and is a systematic method of detection.

B.L. Farberman pedagogical technology about this particular innovation of teaching is the approach. Pedagogical in the management of cognitive activity types of technologies include:

- * Textbook training
- * Classical lecture
- * Training using technical means
- * Advisory system
- Tutoring system

- * Programmable control
 - * Small group system
 - Computer-aided training
- By the main method used pedagogical technologies can be attributed to the following types distinguished:
- * Dogmatic, reproductive
 - * Developmental education
 - * Problematic, research
 - * Creative method
 - Explanatory, visual
 - Programmed learning method
 - Game method
 - * Dialogue method
 - Informative (computerized) education method
 - Self-developing education method

In fact, pedagogical technology independent reading of the reader, knowledge which guarantees to be taught to take, to think is the process. And the methodology is the knowledge, skills of the teacher, skill, personal qualities, temperament related, a particular person is for the teacher convenient teaching methods and ways is a complex.

Historically foreign language teaching methods 4 divided into groups: translation, correct, comparative, mixed. Accordingly, the edge all methods of teaching the language are these 4 grouped into categories. For teaching a foreign language methods of practical use 3: dating, exercise, as well as application. These techniques the tutor organizes. It is these methods through which the student learns and learns a foreign language applies in practice. Having a student have critical thinking while for Teacher different method and pedagogical right to use technology comes. Of the formation of critical thinking there is self-hos technology and it is phased out:

- Knowledge search and independent emphasis on Appropriation
- Previous experience of learners and active use of their knowledge
- All of the relationships own point of view on levels, own expressing the position of sharing ideas promotion
- * Conclusions, judgments
 - positions creating conditions for justification
 - Test new knowledge and experience and encourage attempts to apply.

A developer of critical thinking in pedagogy the following methods and techniques are available:

- Exercise “ goldfish” It is in this technique that students caught goldfish imagines and desires his own says. The band members wish each other hearing, first of all, the grammatical error in it toğirlidi, after which to reach tilagi gives different offers.
- “Art Gallery” This is the student generator app in training through group to 4 or 5 groups, depending on the size divisjon. Teacher quiet classical music puts, a photo that students come to mind draws. This session lasts 5 minutes and when the process is complete, the band members get each other answer the following questions by looking at the picture find:

- ❖ what did you see in the picture?
- ❖ what is "artist" when drawing this pace are you thinking about?
- ❖ what is your opinion on this landscape? - "If I had you in your seat, I.....”

In this exercise, the teacher gives students ask them to say any problem and other students are the solution to this problem must say. Various suggestions that increase critical thinking available and the following as an example we can get;

To search students for information it is necessary to force, as a result of which they can only not limited to the textbook and additional literature and internet thematic information from the network search.

- Critical thinking in students developmental training and give tasks

Feedback on the work performed by students notice, in which the comment is only about how well he did not to be better than that about what it does for - Theory in combination with practical

education it must be carried side by side. I.e. how students put the theory into practice they need to know how to get. Then the students understanding the content of the course and learning process to be more interesting can. - Many creative tasks in the lesson and exercises can be used. This motivates and inspires the student and creativity makes the lesson interesting and effective helps to be. They are not only receive the necessary information, but also satisfaction, satisfaction with the lesson being served form.

The need to increase critical thinking is one there are several reasons and the following are in demand has qualities: - will be independent and analytical - shapes and tests hypotheses - considers other ideas and opinions - can base and explain his ideas Critical thinking is just getting information and different from storage. Critical and logical Bloom in the student to achieve thinking it is advisable to use taxanomy. American famous psychologist and educator Question founded by Benjamin Bloom and the system of assignments-cognitive activity training objectives based on degrees its taxonomy is sufficient in the modern world of Education widely distributed at the level. Training objectives taxonomies of rodent appropriation concrete that flows from a certain level actions, natural interaction of content objects that it becomes more complicated on the basis of dependence categorization by sequential embedding or systematization. Taxonomy-of being classification of complex structured areas and is a theory of systematization.

Many scientists trying to create critical thinking categories did. Bloom taxonomy six of knowledge includes a rank hierarchy:

Bloom's Taxonomy

In the model shown, the level of knowledge of the individual is starting from the so-called basic level and then until reaching a complex level i.e. evaluation develops. This makes taxonomy in various fields we can apply. As well as foreign language very much in

both learning and critical thinking it is important. The reason is, this taxonomy the following are hos to critical thinking abilities include: interpretation, analysis make, evaluate, draw conclusions, explain and self-government.

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